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OPTIMIZATION OF TACTICAL AND TECHNICAL ASPECTS OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF PULMONARY ECHINOCOCCOSIS

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ANNOTATION

The present study is devoted to improving the surgical tactics of treating pulmonary echinococcosis and reducing the recurrence rate. A retrospective and prospective analysis of 207 patients with pulmonary and pleural echinococcosis treated in the multidisciplinary clinic of the Samarkand State Medical University was conducted. The patients were divided into two groups: 98 patients (2010–2016) underwent traditional surgical interventions, and 109 patients (2017–2023) underwent operations using modern technologies. The results of the study showed that the use of mini-thoracotomy and thoracoscopic access for certain indications helps to reduce the trauma of interventions and reduce the recurrence rate. The introduction of intraoperative ultrasound navigation made it possible to accurately determine the localization of cysts and optimize surgical tactics. New diagnostic and therapeutic algorithms aimed at increasing the effectiveness of surgical treatment of thoracic echinococcosis have been developed and proposed.

Key words: pulmonary echinococcosis, surgical treatment, relapses, mini-thoracotomy, thoracoscopy.

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ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ ТАКТИКО – ТЕХНИЧЕСКИХ АСПЕКТОВ ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ЭХИНОКОККОЗА ЛЕГКИХ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Настоящее исследование посвящено совершенствованию хирургической тактики лечения эхинококкоза лёгких и снижению частоты рецидивов. Проведён ретроспективный и проспективный анализ 207 пациентов с эхинококкозом лёгких и плевры, лечившихся в многопрофильной клинике Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета. Пациенты были разделены на две группы: 98 пациентов (2010–2016 гг.) подверглись традиционным хирургическим вмешательствам, а 109 пациентов (2017–2023 гг.) – операциям с применением современных технологий. Результаты исследования показали, что использование мини-торакомотного и торакоскопического доступа при определённых показаниях способствует снижению травматичности вмешательств и уменьшению частоты рецидивов. Внедрение интраоперационной УЗ-навигации позволило точно определять локализацию кист и оптимизировать хирургическую тактику. Разработаны и предложены новые диагностические и лечебные алгоритмы, направленные на повышение эффективности хирургического лечения эхинококкоза органов грудной клетки.

Ключевые слова: эхинококкоз лёгких, хирургическое лечение, рецидивы, мини-торакотомия, торакоскопия.

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О՛ПКА EXINOKOKKOZI XIRURGIK DAVOSINI TAKTIK – TEXNIK JIHATLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu tadqiqot o՛pka exinokokkozini jarrohlik yo՛li bilan davolash taktikasini takomillashtirish va residivlar chastotasini kamaytirishga bag՛ishlangan. Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti ko՛p tarmoqli klinikasida davolangan o՛pka va plevra bo՛shlig՛i exinokokkozi bilan og՛rigan 207 bemorning retrospektiv va prospektiv tahlili o՛tkazildi. Bemorlar ikki guruhga ajratildi: 98 nafar bemor (2010–2016 y.) anʼanaviy jarrohlik amaliyotlarini o՛tkazgan bo՛lsa, 109 nafar bemor (2017–2023 y.) zamonaviy texnologiyalar qo՛llangan jarrohlik usullari bilan davolandi. Tadqiqot natijalari shundan dalolat beradiki, maʼlum ko՛rsatmalar bo՛yicha mini-torakotomiya va torakoskopiya yo՛li bilan jarrohlik amaliyotlarini o՛tkazish jarohatlanish darajasini kamaytirish va residivlar sonini qisqartirish imkonini beradi. Intraoperasion UT-navigasiyani joriy etish exinokokk kistalarining aniq joylashuvini belgilash va jarrohlik taktikasiga tuzatish kiritish imkonini berdi. Ushbu kasallikni jarrohlik yo՛li bilan davolash samaradorligini oshirishga qaratilgan yangi tashxis va davolash algoritmlari ishlab chiqildi va taklif etildi.

Kalit so՛zlar: o՛pka exinokokkozi, jarrohlik davolash, residivlar, mini-torakotomiya, torakoskopiya.

Muammoning dolzarbligi. JSST maʼlumotlariga ko՛ra, exinokokkoz har yili og՛ir asoratlar va o՛lim holatlariga olib keladigan zoonoz parazitlar infeksiyalardan biri bo՛lib qolmoqda. Kasallikning barcha lokalizatsiyalari orasida ko՛krak qafasi aʼzolarining zararlanishi jigar shikastlanishiga qaraganda kamroq uchraydi, ammo u agressiv kechish va hayot uchun xavfli asoratlar yuzaga kelishi bilan tavsiflanadi.

Exinokokkozning o՛pkada klinik kechishi xilma-xil ko՛rinishlar bilan tavsiflanadi — simptomsiz shakllardan tortib, kista yiringlashi, bronxial daraxt yoki plevra bo՛shlig՛iga yorilishi

natijasida pnevmotoraks, empiema va anafilaktik reaksiyalarning rivojlanishigacha bo'lgan og'ir asoratlarga yetishi mumkin.

Xirurgik texnologiyalar takomillashib borishiga qaramay, residivlarning oldini olish, operatsiyadan keyingi davrni samarali boshqarish va rasional antigel'mint terapiya masalalari hal etilmagan qolmoqda.

Turli tadqiqotchilarning tasdiqlangan ma'lumotlariga ko'ra o'pkadan exinokokkektomiyadan so'ng residiv holatlari 2,6% dan 25% gacha tashkil etadi. Residivlar yuqori darajada kuzatilishi faqatgina xirurgik amaliyoti vaqtidagi kontaminasiya bilan emas, balki operatsiyadan keyingi davrda antigel'mint terapiya samaradorligining yetarli emasligi bilan ham bog'liq.

Shunday qilib, ko'krak qafasi a'zolari exinokokkozini xirurgik yo'li bilan davolash natijalarini yaxshilash va residivlar tez-tez uchrashini kamaytirishga qaratilgan yangi tashxis va davolash algoritmlarini ishlab chiqish zamonaviy tibbiyotning dolzarb vazifalaridan biri hisoblanadi.

Tadqiqot maqsadi - jarrohlik taktikasini takomillashtirish va kasallik qaytalanishini kamaytirishning samarali usullarini ishlab chiqish orqali ko'krak qafasi exinokokkozini davolash natijalarini yaxshilash.

Materiallar va tekshirish usullari. Tadqiqot asosiga Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti ko'p tarmoqli klinikasining xirurgiya bo'limiga qabul qilingan o'pka va pleva exinokokkozi bilan og'rikan 207 bemorni davolash natijalari kiritilgan. Davolash taktikasidan kelib chiqib, bemorlar ikki guruhga ajratilgan. Taqqoslash guruhiga 2010-2016 yillar davomida standart tashxisdan so'ng an'anaviy usullar bilan xirurgik amaliyotni o'tkazilgan 98 (47,3%) bemor kiritilgan. 2017 yildan boshlab ko'krak qafasi exinokokkozi bo'yicha xirurgik amaliyotlari zamonaviy texnologiyalardan foydalangan holda takomillashtirilgan. 2017-2023 yillar davomida 109 (52,6%) bemor xirurgik yo'li bilan davolangan va ular asosiy guruhga kiritilgan.

207 nafar ko'krak qafasi exinokokkozi bilan og'rikan bemorlardan 199 nafarida (96,1%) exinokokkoz birinchi marta aniqlangan, 8 nafar bemorda (3,9%) esa residiv qayd etilgan. Shuni ta'kidlab o'tish kerakki, residiv exinokokkoz bilan og'rikan bemorlarning 7 nafarida exinokokkoz kistasi plevra bo'shlig'ida aniqlandi. 207 nafar bemordan 181 nafarida (87,4%) exinokokk kistalari o'rtacha va katta o'lchamga ega bo'lgan. Kistalardagi exinokokk suyuqligining miqdori 100 ml dan 3000 ml gacha o'zgardi.

O'pka exinokokkozida exinokokk kistalarining lokalizatsiyasi bo'yicha ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilganimizda, turli segmentlarda jami 237 ta kista aniqlangan. Biz o'ng o'pkaning ko'proq zararlanishi qayd etilganligini aniqladik, u 113 (54,6%) bemorda kuzatilgan, shulardan 86 (76,1%) nafarida kista pastki bo'lakda joylashgan. Chap o'pkaning izolyasiyalangan zararlanishi 66 (31,9%) bemorda aniqlangan. 28 (13,5%) nafar bemorda exinokokkoz bilan ikkala o'pka zararlanganligi aniqlandi.

Bemorlarning asosiy qismi shifoxonaga rejali ravishda yotqizilgan. Shu sababli, Mel'nikov tasnifi bo'yicha parazitning hayotiy faoliyatining I va II klinik bosqichlarida bo'lgan bemorlar ko'pchilikni, ya'ni 191 (92,3%) nafarni tashkil etdi. Operatsiyagacha bo'lgan davrda, 59 (28,5%) holatda asoratlangan kistalar aniqlandi. Asoratlar strukturasi exinokokk kistasining yiringlashi ustunlik qildi, bu 27 (45,8%) bemorda kuzatildi. Jarrohlik amaliyoti vaqtida 143 (69,1%) holatda sistobronxial oqmalar aniqlandi. Bizning kuzatuvlarimizda kistaning plevra bo'shlig'iga, yoki qorin bo'shlig'iga yorib kirishi kabi asoratlar uchramadi.

Ko'krak qafasi exinokokkozi tashxisi bilan qabul qilingan barcha bemorlarga klinik, laborator va instrumental tekshiruvlar kompleksi o'tkazildi.

O'pka exinokokkozi bo'lgan 207 bemordan 186 (89,5%) nafarida KT tekshiruvi o'tkazildi. KT natijalarini izohlashda o'pka to'qimasining zichligiga alohida e'tibor qaratib, jigar to'qimasining zichligi bilan solishtirdik.

Tadqiqot natijalari. Taqqoslash guruhidagi 98 nafar bemorda jami 110 ta jarrohlik aralashuvlari amalga oshirilgan (12 nafar bemorda ikkala o'pka zararlanishi bo'lgan). Shulardan 11 (110 aralashuvning 10,0%) amaliyotda o'pkadan exinokokkektomiya mitorakotomiya orqali o'tkazilgan. 99 (110 aralashuvning 90,0%) amaliyot keng torakotomiya orqali bajarilib, ularning 12 tasida (12,1%) keng torakotomiya ikki marotaba amalga oshirilgan.

109 nafar asosiy guruhdagi bemorlarda 125 ta jarrohlik amaliyoti o'tkazilgan. Shulardan 58 nafar (46,4%) bemorda, jami to'plangan ball 10 dan 24 gacha bo'lgan holatlarda qovurg'alar orasidan keng oldingi yon va yon torakotomiya qo'llanildi. 6ta holatda minitorakotom kesimdan exinokokkektomiya qilish texnik qiyinchiliklar to'g'dirganligi sababli keng torakotomiyaga, ya'ni konversiyaga o'tildi.

Asosiy guruhdagi 32 (25,6%) nafar bemorda minitorakotomiyani amalga oshirish uchun, kesimdan oldin UTT navigasiyasida kista joylashgan joyini aniqlab minitorakotom kesim belgilandi. Bu kistalarning aniq lokalizatsiyasini aniqlashga yordam berdi. Minitorakotom kirish usuli qo'llanilgan barcha bemorlarda kista periferiyada joylashgan bo'lib, uning devori parietal plevrage yaqin edi (rasm 1).

Rasm 1. UTT navigasiyasida kista joylashgan joyini aniqlab minitorakotom kesimni belgilash

Jami to'plangan ballar 5 dan kam bo'lgan 13 (10,4%) nafar bemorlarda o'pkadan exinokokkektomiya torakoskopik usulda amalga oshirildi. Bular exinokokkning E. Veterinorum modifikatsiyasi, ya'ni qiz pufakchalari bo'lmagan kistaga ega bo'lgan bemorlar edi (rasm 2).

Rasm 2. O'pkadan torakoskopik exinokokkektomiya

Shunday qilib, o'pkada exinokokkoz lokalizatsiyasining topik verifikatsiyasi va kasallik og'irlik darajasini balli baholash, kistalar soni, ularning o'lchami, shuningdek, asoratlar xususiyati va mavjudligini hisobga olish, asosiy guruhda 43,2% holatda exinokokkektomiyani minitorakotom kirish orqali va 10,4% holatda torakoskopik usulda bajarish imkonini berdi. Shuningdek, an'anaviy keng torakotom kirishlar sonini 56,8% ga qisqartirishga erishildi. Minitorakotom kesim orqali operatsiya davomiyligi qiyosiy guruh bemorlari bilan solishtirganda $92,3 \pm 5,2$ minutdan $63,5 \pm 1,8$ minutgacha qisqartirildi.

Yuqorida qayd etilgan yangiliklarni amaliyotga joriy etish natijasida drenajlar bilan ambulator davolanishga chiqarilgan bemorlar soni 25,4% dan 4,0% gacha kamaydi (jadval 1).

Jadval 1.

O'pka exinokokkozi bilan bemorlarda operatsiyadan keyingi davrning kechishi

Ko'rsatkichlar	Taqqoslash guruhi (n=110)	Asosiy guruh (n=125)
Minitorakotomiyada operatsiyaning davomiyligi, daqiqa	92,3±3,4	63,5±1,3
Keng torakotomiyada operatsiyaning davomiyligi, daqiqa	106,2±4,2	80,3±2,1
Isitma davomiyligi, sut.	7,2±1,2	1,3±0,1
Koyko-kunlar soni:		
- operatsiyagacha, sut.	3,2±1,3	1,3±0,7
- RvITB, sut.	2,4±0,9	1,1±0,02
- Operatsiyadan keyin, sut.	7,3±2,05	4,2±1,07
- Jami, sut.	13,1±4,3	7,4±1,7
Qoldiq bo'shliqdan drenajni olib tashlash muddatlari, sut.	16,3±1,2	14,9±1,7
Plevra bo'shlig'idan drenajni olib tashlash muddatlari, sut.	4,3±1,05	2,3±0,1
Drenaj bilan javob berilgan bemorlar soni, abs. (%)	28 (25,4%)	5 (4,0%)

Intraoperasion asoratlar 6,4% dan 1,6%gacha kamaydi. Operatsiyadan keyingi erta davrda asoratlar 13,6% dan 1,6% gacha kamaydi (jadval 2).

Jadval 2.

O'pka exinokokkozini jarrohlik davolashning bevosita natijalari

Asorat turi	Taqqoslash guruhi, n=110		Asosiy guruh, n=125		Jami, n=235	
	abs.	%	abs.	%	abs.	%
Intraoperatsion asoratlar						
Anafilaktik shok	2	1,8	0	0	2	0,8
Intraoperasion qon ketish	2	1,8	1	0,8	3	1,3
Kista elementlarining atrof to'qimalarga tarqalishi	3	2,7	1	0,8	4	1,7
Jami intraoperasion asoratlar	7	6,4	2	1,6	9	3,8
Erta operatsiyadan keyingi davrdagi asoratlar						
Qoldiq bo'shliqning yiringlashi	3	2,7	0	0	3	1,3
Plevrit	3	2,7	0	0	3	1,3
Qon tupurish	6	5,4	2	1,6	8	3,4
Operatsiyadan keyingi jarohatning yiringlashi	3	2,7	0	0	3	1,3
Erta operatsiyadan keyingi davrdagi jami asoratlar	15	13,6	2	1,6	17	7,2
Erta operatsiyadan keyingi davrda asorat kuzatilgan bemorlar soni	12	10,9	2	1,6	14	5,9

Exinokokkoz sababli jarrohlik amaliyoti o'tkazilgan 207 bemordan 144 (69,6%) nafarida kechki natijalar tahlil qilindi. Kechki muddatlarda o'rganilgan 144 bemordan 14 (9,7%) nafarida exinokokkozning qaytalanishi kuzatilib, 2010-2016 yy. davomida operatsiya o'tkazilgan taqqoslash guruhidagi bemorlar orasida ushbu ko'rsatkich 16,0% ni tashkil etdi Yuqoridagi innovasiyalar va

kasallikning oldini olish chora-tadbirlarini qo'llash natijasida asosiy guruhda kasallik qaytalanish holatlarini 2,9% gacha kamaytirishga muvaffaq bo'ldik. Asosiy guruhda qaytalanish holatlari kamayishini biz asoratlangan kistalarda taranlashgan, kal'siylangan fibroz kapsulalar mavjud bo'lgan hollarda radikal jarrohlik usullariga o'tish bilan bog'laymiz.

Xulosalar:

1. O'pka exinokokkozi joylashuvini topik aniqlash, hamda kistalar soni, ularning o'lchami, asoratlar mavjudligi va ularning xususiyatlarini hisobga olgan holda kasallik kechishining og'irlik darajasini ballarda baholashning tavsiya etilgan diagnostik algoritmi asosiy guruhdagi 53,6% holatda kam invaziv usulda, xususan minitorakotom kesim orqali (43,2%), hamda endovideoxirurgik usulda (10,4%) adekvat exinokokkektomiya bajarish imkonini berdi. Ushbu orqali an'anaviy keng kesimlar bajarish 56,8% (χ^2 mezonining qiymati 213.345ni tashkil etdi; erkinlik darajalari soni – 2 ni; ahamiyatlilik darajasi esa $p < 0,001$ ni tashkil etdi) gacha qisqardi, operatsiya davomiyligi esa minitorakotom kesim orqali taqqoslash guruhidagi bemorlar bilan taqqoslanganda $92,3 \pm 5,2$ dan $63,5 \pm 1,8$ minutgacha qisqardi, (t -mezon = 5,07; $p < 0,001$).

2. Ko'krak qafasi a'zolari exinokokkozida xirurgik taktikani tanlash algoritmi, radikal exinokokkektomiya va qoldiq bo'shliqni bartaraf qilish ustunligi bilan kompleks yondashuni hisobga olib kesimni tanlash, shuningdek profilaktik kimyoterapiya operatsiyadan keyingi erta davrdagi asoratlarni 13,6%dan 1,6%gacha ($p = 0,027$ χ^2 mezon bo'yicha) va kasallik qaytalanishini 16,0%dan 2,9%gacha ($p = 0,031$ χ^2 mezon bo'yicha) qisqartirish bilan ko'rsatilayotgan tibbiy yordam sifatini yaxshilashga erishildi.

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